

THE BUCKLING OF RECTANGULAR COMPOSITE PLATES WITH CUTOUT UNDER UNIAXIAL AND BIAXIAL COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Here the buckling strength of the simply supported plate with a centrally located circular cutout under uniaxial and biaxial compressive loading is demonstrated by using FEM. The composite materials consisting of carbon-fiber/epoxy and glass-fiber/epoxy are treated as the case of angle-ply and cross-ply rectangular orthotropic plates. The buckling value for the variation of cutout size and the buckled pattern mode for different aspect ratio of the plate are elucidated in the present study.

In case of both in cross-ply and angle-ply laminated plates under uniaxial compression, it is shown that the buckling value for increasing hole size appears higher than the plate with no-hole at a certain range of the plate aspect ratio. As for the effect of the lamination angle, the buckling resistance at $\theta=+45^\circ$ becomes higher than any other angle. The buckled wave of the longer plate goes on higher number modes as the lamination angle is high degrees. The buckling value of the plate under biaxial compression is reduced when the hole dimensions are gradually large for all the biaxial loading ratios. Higher order waves of buckled mode toward longitudinal direction of the plate with cutout appears hardly for all the aspect ratios.

KEYWORDS: Buckling; Biaxial; Cutout; Rectangular FRP Plates; Finite Element Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials such as carbon-fiber reinforced plastics have been used for the various parts and members in light-weight structures, because of their high specific strength and stiffness. The buckling behavior associated with composite rectangular plates with cutout under compressive loading is an interesting engineering problem to study. The cutout exists for the necessity such as access ports and various operating holes of the structures. It often offers that the damage of the structural members as the reduction of buckling resistance is caused by the presence of cutout. Several researchers for the buckling behavior of composite plate with cutout have been presented as shown in references 1 to 6. Most of their studies are treated as the buckling of square or rectangular plates for composites under uniaxial compression. This paper considers the buckled resistance and modes for rectangular composite plates having the variation

of cutout dimensions under axial compression. The scheme of scope in this study comprises (a) 3 types of orthotropic plate as for 0° & 90° cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ and angle-ply $[\pm\theta^\circ]$, (b) composites as for CFRP and GFRP rectangular plates, and (c) compressive loading as for uniaxial and biaxial loading.

2. MODELS OF COMPOSITE PLATE

Numerical results by using FEM are obtained for the plates having the fundamental elastic constants of carbon-fiber/epoxy and glass-fiber/epoxy composites with fiber volume content $V_f=60\%$ as indicate in Table 1. These constants for FRP can be estimated by algebraic formulae when constituent materials and V_f are specified (see ref. 7). The constitutive equation of the force and moment resultants are shown in terms of the middle surface extensional strains and curvatures as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix}$$

where the term of $A_{16}, A_{26}, D_{16}, D_{26}$ and $B_{ij}(i,j=1,2,6)$ vanishes in each case of this study. The lamination angle ($\pm\theta$) is varied in the range of $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$

The plate aspect ratio (a: the plate length, b: the plate width) is varied in the range of $a/b \leq 4.0$. The value of buckling resistance is presented as the non-dimensional parameter (see ref.4) $\lambda = Pcr \cdot b / E_T \cdot t^3$. The boundary conditions of the plate edges are all simply supported. The configuration of cutout is a circular hole which is located at the center of the plate. The number of buckled half wave modes in the x- and y-direction defines as n for direction of the plate width and m for direction of the plate length.

The plate usually buckles into a single half wave $n=1$, in the y-direction. As the plate aspect ratio increases, the plate buckles to vary into a single or more and more buckled half waves in the x-direction. Biaxial compressive loading ratio's parameter is expressed as $K_y = N_y / N_x$, where N_y and N_x are compressive resultant forces in each direction, respectively.

3. SPECIALLY ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATES

3.1 Uniaxial compression loading Buckling loads for rectangular specially orthotropic laminated plates under uniform compression for CFRP are obtained in Fig.1 which shows λ versus a/b curves. For small aspect ratio at $\theta=0^\circ$, see Fig.1(a), the increase of cutout size shows evidently the reduction

FIGURE 1. Relation between λ and a/b for specially orthotropic plates under uniaxial compression

TABLE 1 FUNDAMENTAL ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF MATERIALS

Constants Materials	E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_L	ν_T	G_{LT} (GPa)	E_L/E_T
CFRP	136.6	8.17	0.3160	0.019	4.75	16.73
GFRP	44.7	12.37	0.2570	0.071	4.64	3.61
Isotropic	72.5		0.340		27.1	1.00

$V_f=60\%$

of λ and the plate buckles into a single half wave in the x-direction. For long aspect ratio of changing from a single wave to another, λ of the plate with cutout is higher value than that of the solid(non-hole) plate. The buckling value for $\theta=90^\circ$ as shown in Fig.1(b) becomes all lower than that of the solid plate. As the plate aspect ratio increase, the plate buckles into higher order buckled half waves to the x-direction and λ versus a/b curves get flat trend. For the large cutout size as $d/b > 0.3$, buckled waves are governed by odd number modes. The buckling value as the plates with small cutout $d/b=0.1$ gets almost the same value compared with λ of the solid plate.

3.2 Biaxial compressive loading Fig.2 provides buckling state for rectangular simply supported specially orthotropic plates with cutout loaded by biaxial loading ratio $K_y=1.0$. The buckling values become rather low estimation compared with the plate under uniaxial compressive loading. As the plate aspect ratio increases, λ becomes gradual decrease for all the plates of $\theta=0^\circ$, respectively, in Fig.2(a). The buckled half waves for all the plates appeared only one mode in x-direction. In the case of plates $\theta=90^\circ$, variations of the buckled value are very little in spite of the aspect ratio increases as shown in Fig.2(b). The buckling behavior for wave modes is similar to the plate subjected to uniaxial compression, though the buckling resistance of the plate loaded by biaxial compression shows lower value.

FIGURE 2. Relation between λ and a/b for specially orthotropic plates under biaxial compression

4. CROSS-PLY ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATES

4.1 Uniaxial compressive loading The buckling behavior of orthotropic cross-ply laminated plates with cutout are shown in Fig.3. As for the comparison of the buckling values between CFRP and GFRP composites, it is found the higher orthotropic ratio (E_L/E_T) as CFRP plate obtains the higher buckled resistance for all the plates. Both CFRP and GFRP solid plates are changing the buckling mode at each point of $a/b=1.5$ & 2.5 . In solid plates, minimum buckling value λ appeared at the integral numbers of the aspect ratio. The presence of cutout makes a difference of buckling mode behavior against the solid plates. The aspect range being $m=2$ tends to get more narrow region according as the cutout size increases. In the case of the plate with large hole, the buckling value is much higher than the solid plate as the range becomes still more narrow. It is considered that the in-plane stress state for the perforated plate is different for each the plate aspect ratio. For the large cutout, there are interactions of the tensile membrane stress region which has broadly extension toward loading and unloading edges of the plate from the stress distribution around the hole in the plane. The buckling values for CFRP plate are approximately three times higher than GFRP plate for all the aspect ratios in $0.5 < a/b < 4.0$. The distribution of the membrane tensile stress area for CFRP plate with

FIGURE 3. Comparison of the buckling for CFRP and GFRP cross-ply orthotropic plates under uniaxial compression

$d/b=0.5$ is showed in Fig.4. Comparing the tensile stress states for the aspect ratio $a/b=1.7$ and $a/b=1.0$ (square plate), the stress area in the plate for the ratio $a/b=1.7$ which obtained the highest buckling resistance from Fig.3 becomes much more expansion of distribution. The appearance of a full sine wave $m=2$ such as the rectangular plate with large cutout also shows rather high buckling resistance.

FIGURE 4. Distribution of tensile stress

4.2 Biaxial compressive loading

Buckling behavior of the rectangular plates subjected to biaxial compression is influenced by the biaxial loading ratio K_y as shown in Fig.5. For the solid plate under uniaxial compression, the buckled half waves m in x -direction varies to a number of higher order modes as the plate aspect ratio becomes large. The buckling value which the biaxial loading ratio changes to $K_y=0.5, 1.0$ and 2.0 from $K_y=0$ goes with reduction. In case of the rectangular plates under $K_y=1.0$ & 2.0 , the buckling value has dropped sharply until a/b comes to about 1.5 and the value of the aspect ratio over $a/b=1.5$ is roughly same estimated. As shown in Fig.6, all the plates with cutout under $K_y=0.5$ appear the change of buckled mode at certain aspect ratio. After showing the rapid decrease of the buckling

FIGURE 5. Effect of K_y for the solid plate

FIGURE 6. λ - a/b curves for $K_y=0.5$

FIGURE 7. λ - a/b curves for $K_y=2.0$

value up to $a/b=1.0$, square plate, the λ shows a slightly increase till the buckled modes appear to change to the another wave mode at each aspect ratio. The large perforated plate such as with $d/b=0.3$ & 0.5 shows the change of wave mode from $m=1$ to $m=3$ at considerable long plate, $a/b > 2.5$. To assess the influence of changing the plate aspect ratio on the buckling behavior under biaxial loading ratio $K_y=2$ for each cutout, the result is shown in Fig.7. As cutout sizes become larger, the buckling value of the plate is always low estimation under any aspect ratio. The λ versus a/b curves of buckling behavior shows similar trend for each case of the perforated plate. Higher buckling waves besides $m=1$ never appear even though the plate length becomes longer.

5. ANGLE-PLY ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATES

5.1 Square plate under uni- and bi-axial compressive loading Uniaxial buckling for CFRP square orthotropic angle-ply plate at the lamination angle $\pm\theta$ with cutout is shown in Fig.8. Although the highest buckling resistance is obtained at $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$, which shows non-hole or small hole ($d/b=0.1$) plate, the buckling value of the plates with large hole tends to get more over the lamination angle than $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$. It is found that the effect of cutout size appears sensitively in less than $\theta=\pm 55^\circ$. However, at the large lamination angle that is over $\theta=\pm 60^\circ$, it shows that the rapid buckling reduction in accordance with changing to the another modes occurs for any kind of the perforated plates. The buckling values over $\theta=\pm 60^\circ$ are almost the same. There are little influence of the cutout sizes.

The buckling behavior for CFRP plate under biaxial compression is shown in Fig.9. Biaxial loading ratio $K_y=1$, that is subjected to the same loading both in x- and y-direction, it is a matter of course that the highest resistance on each lamination angle occurs at $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$ which is symmetrical behavior with respect to the angle. It also shows that the buckled mode of the perforated plate appears only a single half wave except the plate with $d/b=0.1$. For large hole sizes such as $d/b=0.3$ & 0.5 , there are not much differences between the buckling values of the plates in the range of the angle $\pm 20^\circ < \theta < \pm 70^\circ$.

FIGURE 8. Buckling of angle-ply square plate under uniaxial loading

FIGURE 9. Buckling of angle-ply square plate under biaxial loading

5.2 Rectangular plate under uniaxial compressive loading Fig.10 shows the buckling state of the perforated rectangular plate under uniaxial compression with respect to any kind of lamination angle θ . The buckling resistance becomes higher as the lamination angle varies from $\theta=0^\circ$ up to $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$. The higher buckling value of those plates is obtained at $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$ for each of the aspect ratio. And as further increasing the angle, a decreasing tendency is seen. (no inset as Figure)

The buckled mode of the plate appeared corresponding to each natural number

FIGURE 10. Effect of the lamination angle for buckling

FIGURE 11. λ - a/b curves for the perforated plates at $0 \pm 45^\circ$

1,2,3,.. in any changing case of the angle up to $\theta \pm 45^\circ$ throughout the plate aspect ratio's range. For the plate with large cutout as $d/b=0.3$, the mode only appears the odd number half waves at $\theta > 45^\circ$.

It is assumed to be obtained the higher buckling resistance at $\theta \pm 45^\circ$ whichever the aspect ratio, so the buckling behavior of the plate for each hole size is presented in Fig.11. The figure indicates that the change to mode $m=2$ is but little as the hole size increases in the aspect ratio range $1.5 < a/b < 2.0$. For the large hole as $d/b=0.5$, the buckling resistance of the plate gains much higher than that of the non-hole plate. The figure recognizes that the least amount of buckling resistance is exhibited by the perforated plate with $d/b=0.3$.

To assess the wave mode transition on the buckling, the image simulation patterns for the rectangular plates under uniaxial compression in case of $\theta \pm 45^\circ$ and $d/b=0.5$ are shown in Fig.12. As the plate becomes longer, the buckled wave in x-direction is changing to the higher order modes and the resistance also changes for each the aspect. The buckled mode in y-direction usually appears only a single half wave $n=1$ for the perforated plates.

FIGURE 12. Buckled mode patterns

5.3 Rectangular plate under biaxial compressive loading The effect of the lamination angle on the buckling of the rectangular perforated plate under biaxial loading with compression, $Ky=1.0$, is shown in Fig.13. The buckling value of changing the lamination angle up to $\theta \pm 70^\circ$, where shows the highest resistance, is gradually increased. In the range of the angle $0^\circ < \theta < \pm 30^\circ$, the buckling value for all the plates is not much difference. After showing the highest buckling resistance at $\theta \pm 70^\circ$ for all the plates, the buckling value is getting a further decrease, and the higher number modes in the perforated plate occur in the range of over $\theta \pm 70^\circ$. The state of changing of buckled mode is similar for two representative hole sizes, $d/b=0.3$ and 0.5 . Also as further increasing the biaxial loading ratio, such as $Ky=2$ or 3 , the highest resistance occurs at some $\theta \pm 70^\circ$. Fig.14 shows the influence of changing the plate aspect ratio on the buckling under biaxial loading ratio $Ky=1.0$ for $\theta \pm 30^\circ$ laminates. As the plate becomes longer, the buckling resistance is on the decrease. The values are almost similar estimation which has no influence between cutout dimensions.

FIGURE 13. Effect of lamination angle under $K_y=1.0$ & $a/b=3.0$

FIGURE 14. Buckling of rectangular plate under $K_y=1.0$ at $\theta=\pm 30^\circ$

The comparison of buckling strength reduction ratio under biaxial loading ratio $K_y=3.0$, defined as the ratio of the perforated plate λ to the solid plate λ_N , is shown in Fig.15. For the rectangular plate $a/b=2.0$, the tendency is toward a nearly linear decline in order as the cutout dimensions increase for all the lamination angles. There is a rather influence of the angle for the large perforated plate. The plate at $\theta=\pm 30^\circ$ gives a fairly good performance as compared with the others for the full range of cutout dimensions. The smaller the angle becomes as in order of $\theta=\pm 60^\circ, \pm 45^\circ$, and $\pm 30^\circ$, the better the performance shows. The specially orthotropic plate shows a poor performance compared with the angle-ply laminates. These results understand as was stated previously. The behavior for the reduction of the perforated plate under biaxial loading is different from the case of uniaxial compressive loading.

FIGURE 15. Buckling reduction for each angle θ

6. CONCLUSION

An investigation was carried out to examine the buckling behavior for rectangular FRP composite plates with cutout under uniaxial and biaxial compressive loading. Results of the buckled plates are numerically obtained by using FEM. The buckling behavior for each composite plate with a circular hole, which varies parameters for changing the plate aspect ratio, cutout dimension and the lamination angle, is mainly concluded as follows.

Uniaxial compression: In the case of both in cross ply and angle ply orthotropic plates, it shows that the buckling value for increasing hole size appears higher than the solid(non-hole) plates at a certain range of the aspect ratio. As for the effect of the lamination angle the buckling value at $\theta=\pm 45^\circ$ becomes higher than the others. The buckling deformation waves of the long plate goes on higher number modes to loading direction as the lamination angle is high degrees.

Biaxial compression: The buckling value of the plate is reduced when the hole dimension is gradually large for all the biaxial loading ratios. The reduction shows remarkable discrimination compared with the uniaxial loading. Higher number waves of buckled modes to longitudinal direction of the plate with cutout appear hardly for all the aspect ratios. For specially orthotropic plates, the buckled modes at $\theta=90^\circ$ are similar to the plate subjected

to uniaxial compression as behavior. Although the buckling value is influenced by the variation of the loading ratio and cutout dimension, it shows to converge the value wherein the short range aspect ratio for cross-ply plates as the loading ratio becomes large. For angle-ply plates, the highest buckling resistance of the long plate under biaxial loading shows at $\theta = \pm 70^\circ$ of all the lamination angles. The smaller the lamination angle orientates, the better the performance of resistance for buckling reduction shows.

7. REFERENCES

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